

Selenito-Complexes. Normal Selenites of Transition Metals

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A general method for the preparation of normal selenites of transition metals is described. The normal selenites of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} were prepared by reacting the corresponding acetates with excess selenous acid in aqueous acetic acid media. The electronic absorption spectra and the magnetic moments of the complexes show that they have octahedral configurations. Ir spectra show that the selenite group acts as a bridge, linking the metal atoms in a polymeric structure.

A previous trial¹ to prepare normal selenites of Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} by reacting sodium selenite with the corresponding metal nitrates in aqueous solutions yielded the following basic selenites: $\text{NiSeO}_3 \cdot \text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $5\text{CoSeO}_3 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($n=15, 17$ or 19), $3\text{MnSeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{Mn}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $3\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $3\text{Fe}_2(\text{SeO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The formation of these basic selenites rather than normal selenites was attributed to the hydrolysis of sodium selenite in aqueous solution and thus the reaction medium was slightly alkaline.

This paper describes a general method for the preparation of normal transition metal selenites in acidic medium so as to avoid the contamination of the selenites with the basic salts.

Experimental

Selenium dioxide (Merck) was used as such. Copper(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), chromium(III), manganese(II), iron(III) nitrates and/or acetates, sodium hydroxide, ammonium hydroxide and acetic acid were reagent grade chemicals.

Preparation of the selenites :

Method (1) : Selenium dioxide in excess (2 : 1 mole ratio) was dissolved in 50% acetic acid (100 ml)

and warmed to 60°. The solution was then added to a stirred solution of the transition metal acetate in hot glacial acetic acid (100 ml). The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with 50% acetic acid, methanol and then ether.

Method (2) : The transition metal hydroxide was precipitated from the corresponding nitrate either by adding sodium hydroxide or ammonium hydroxide as cited in the literature. The hydroxides were washed with water and stirred with a slight excess of selenous acid at 80°. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed with water, ethanol and ether.

Analysis : The selenite compounds were dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluted with water. The selenite ion was reduced with sodium sulphite and the precipitated selenium filtered ; metal ions in filtrate was then estimated by complexometric titration using EDTA. Selenium was estimated by reducing the selenite ion with potassium iodide and titrating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate solution. Hydrogen was estimated at the Fine Chemical Analysis Centre, Cairo University. Results are shown in Table 1.

Spectra and magnetic moment : The ir spectra were recorded in the range 4000 – 400 cm^{-1} on KBr disc using a Pye-Unicam SP 1100 spectrometer,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF NORMAL SELENITES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
				M	Se	H
1.	$\text{NiSeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light green	Changes to greenish yellow at 210	26.4 (26.5)	34.7 (35.6)	2.9 (1.8)
2.	$\text{CoSeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Mauve	Changes to violet at 190	26.5 (26.6)	36.1 (35.6)	2.5 (1.8)
3.	$\text{MnSeO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light pink	> 220	27.5 (27.5)	39.3 (39.5)	1.5 (1.0)
4.	$\text{CuSeO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light blue	Changes to yellowish green at 195	27.8 (28.1)	35.5 (34.9)	2.7 (1.8)
5.	$\text{Cr}_2(\text{SeO}_3)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Green	> 220	19.2 (19.3)	44.4 (44.0)	2.3 (1.1)
6.	$\text{Fe}_2(\text{SeO}_3)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Orange brown	> 220	20.4 (20.4)	49.1 (49.3)	1.9 (1.1)

TABLE 2—OBSERVED IR FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF THE SELENITE GROUP IN NORMAL SELENITES

Compd. no. ^a	$\nu_1(\text{A}')$	$\nu_2(\text{A}')$	$\nu_3(\text{A}')$	$\nu_4(\text{A}')$	$\nu_5(\text{A}'')$	$\nu_6(\text{A}'')$
1	845s,b 805s,b	710vs,b	570m,b	465m,sh	665s,sh	320m
2	810s,b	700vs,b	575w,b	490s,b 455m,sh	665s,sh	305m
3	855vs	760vs,b	—	455s 435s	685vs,b	—
4	815s,sh 780s b	730vs,sh 710vs,b 690vs,b	560s,br	430m,b 460m,b	660s sh	352m
5	850s,sh	750vs,b	560m b	480w,b	695s,sh	340m
6	870m,sh 880m,sh 805m,sh	725vs,b	520w,b	470m,b	690s,sh	—

^a As in Sl. no. of Table 1.

and in the range 400–250 cm^{-1} in nujol between polyethylene plates on a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrometer. Electronic spectra of the solids were recorded on a Beckman Acta MIV spectrophotometer provided with a diffuse reflectance attachment. Magnetic measurements were carried out at 20° by the Gouy method.

Results and Discussion

The prepared normal selenites are crystalline compounds and insoluble in all common solvents. The preparation of manganese(II) selenite was carried out in a buffer solution of sodium acetate and acetic acid (pH 5.5), otherwise a diselenite, MnSe_2O_5 , was obtained. Koskenlinna *et al.*⁸ observed that there is an equilibrium between the manganese(II) selenite and the diselenite in aqueous solution. The equilibrium is pH-dependent and shifts toward the formation of the diselenite as the pH is lowered. Chromium(III) selenite prepared by method (2) was always contaminated with the basic salt. Ferric selenite was reduced to ferrous selenite when left in aqueous solution in contact with an excess of selenous acid for 30 days. It is noteworthy that ferrous ions reduce the selenite ion *in situ* to selenium in acidic medium⁹.

Magnetic moments and spectra: The ir frequencies of the selenite group in normal selenites are given in Table 2. X-Ray studies showed that the SeO_3^{2-} group acts as a bridge between three metal atoms, *i.e.* as a tridentate ligand⁴⁻¹¹. As the Se—O bonds and OSeO angles are unequal, the symmetry of the selenite group is C_2 and there are six normal vibrations, three stretching vibrations at 780–870, 690–760 and 660–695 cm^{-1} and three bending vibrations at 520–575, 430–490 and 320–360 cm^{-1} . The observed splitting of the stretching vibrations in the spectrum of copper(II) selenite could be due to the distortion of its octahedral configuration which was further evident from X-ray analysis⁶. This distortion also lead to further distortion of the trigonal pyramidal configuration

of the SeO_3^{2-} group. The ir spectra of normal selenites showed also broad stretching and bending vibrations of coordinated water molecules at 2 850–3 500 and 1 510–1 650 cm^{-1} , respectively. Splitting of the stretching vibrations to three or four peaks and the bending vibrations of two peaks was observed in the case of some selenites, as shown in Table 3. The presence of the lower stretching and bending vibrations indicates H-bonding between water molecules and the oxygen atoms of the selenite group.

TABLE 3—OBSERVED IR FREQUENCIES OF WATER MOLECULES

Compd. no. ^a	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	
	Stretching	Bending
1	3 470, 3 220, 2 930	1 630, 1 530
2	3 440, 3 220, 2 960	1 615, 1 510
3	3 430	1 620
4	3 510, 3 190, 2 930, 2 850	1 650, 1 550
5	3 500 2 9 0	1 630, 1 580
6	3 420, 3 220, 2 930	1 630

^a As in Sl. no. of Table 1.

The visible spectral data and magnetic moment values of the normal selenites are shown in Table 4. There are three bands in the solid state electronic spectra of nickel(II) selenite and the medium energy band is split into a doublet due to distortion from octahedral symmetry. The spectra of cobalt(II) selenite showed three bands of which the medium energy band was difficult to locate due to its low intensity. The high energy band was accompanied by a shoulder at a higher frequency. For the manganese(II) selenite (d^5) the absorption was very weak to be characterised. Copper(II) selenite (d^9) showed one asymmetric band. Chromium(III) selenite showed only two bands, the third one being obscured by the charge transfer band. The lowest energy band consists of a main band and a shoulder at a lower frequency. Iron(III) has sextet ground state and since all other terms of higher energy are of a different spin multiplicity, electronic transitions

TABLE 4—MAGNETIC MOMENT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF HIGH-SPIN SIX-COORDINATE SELENITO COMPLEXES

Compd. no.*	μ_{eff} B.M.	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		
		ν_1	ν_2	ν_3
1	3.05	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ 8 830	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ 13 250 - 14 700	${}^3A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ 24 700
2	4.84 °	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ 7 690	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ 15 040	${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ 18 870 - 20 200(sh)
3	5.51	No spin-allowed transitions		
4	1.82	${}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ 14 290		
5	3.38	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ 14 290 16 260	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ 22 470	${}^4A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ —
6	4.70	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6T_1(G)$ 11 860	${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^6T_2(G)$ 20 400	${}^6I_1 \rightarrow {}^6A_1, {}^6E(G)$ 25 000

* As in Sl. no. of Table 1.

are thus spin-forbidden. However, due to lowering in the symmetry of the compound three absorption bands appeared.

The magnetic moment values obtained at room temperature are somewhat low for magnetically normal octahedral complexes, and this may be due to antiferromagnetic exchange between adjacent transition metal ions in a chain-like, ligand-bridged polymeric structure.

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